

Gender Politics and the Sense of Revolt against Patriarchy: A Reading in the Poetry of Selected Modern American Women-Poets

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Abstract

The feminist movement has undergone different and critical phases in its history ranging from peaceful protests to violent reactions and it has assumed an aggressive dimension in the Western world, particularly in America and France a long time ago. In many countries, it is only beginning to witness the activity of self-actualization, assertiveness and independence by women. Despite the fact that the power of the female emerged in the Western hemisphere, many women are still compelled to put on a mask, a veil and a type of purdah in many countries of the world. This piece of research attempts to examine the politics of feminism in the poetry of Elizabeth Bishop, Anne Sexton, and Adrienne Rich. The findings of this study reveal that Elizabeth Bishop maintains a reticent and covert kind of feminism where she revolts against the male's exploitation of the woman's body and expresses her regret for the loss of romantic and spiritual love, Anne Sexton makes out of her bitter experiences a catalyst for women to struggle for their rights, while Adrienne Rich takes feminism to its extremes as she calls for a rigorous and radical revision of the existing Western culture which is based on patriarchal principles.

Keywords: Feminist movement, patriarchy, American poetry, women-poets, values

السياسات النسوية وتمثلات التمرد على النظام الأبوي: دراسة في شعر نخبة من الشاعرات الأمريكيات الحديثات

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الملخص

لقد مرّت الحركة النسوية بمراحل متعدّدة وحاسمة في تاريخها، تراوحت بين الاحتجاجات السلمية وردود الأفعال العنيفة، وقد اتخذت بُعدًا هجوميًا في العالم الغربي، ولا سيما في أمريكا وفرنسا منذ زمن بعيد. وفي العديد من البلدان الأخرى، ولكن الحركة لا تزال في بداياتها وتشهد الآن بروز نشاطات متعلّقة بتحقيق الذات، وإثبات الوجود، والاستقلالية لدى النساء. ورغم أنّ قوة المرأة برزت أولاً في النصف الغربي من العالم، إلا أنّ كثيرًا من النساء ما زلن مجبرات على أشكالٍ من العزلة الاجتماعية في عدد كبير من دول العالم..

يسعى هذا البحث إلى دراسة سياسة النسوية في شعر إليزابيث بيشوب، وأن سيكستون، وأدريان ريتش. وتكشف نتائج هذه الدراسة أن إليزابيث بيشوب تمثّل نسوية متحفّظة وخفيّة، إذ تتمرّد على استغلال الرجل لجسد المرأة وتعبر عن أسفها لفقدان الحب الرومانسي والروحي. أما آن سيكستون، فقد حوّلت تجاربها المريرة إلى محفّز يدفع النساء إلى النضال من أجل حقوقهن. في حين أنّ أدريان ريتش دفعت بالنسوية إلى أقصى مدياتها، إذ دعت إلى مراجعة صارمة وجذرية للثقافة الغربية القائمة على المبادئ الأبوية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الحركة النسوية، السلطة الأبوية، الشعر الأمريكي، الشاعرات النسوية، القيم

Introduction

With all its inherent vices, patriarchal society has consolidated its grip on the daily activities of women including codes of cladding. According to Mujahid Alwaqaa (2022), this grip is consolidated by nuclear families, mass media, and consumerism which have strengthened and perpetuated the bourgeois and gender-based values and taboos. Society tends to stand by man and unfairly censures woman for domestic and sexual faults. The limited experiences of women outside the house curb them from developing a more productive life and establishing more authentic identities. They become an easy prey, and they are prone to victimization, domestic and social abuse and exploitation. Being sensitive to social reprimand and degradation, some women writers such as Elizabeth Bishop could not directly approach women's critical problems. Such writers are always ready to strike a compromise with a male-dominated society.

As feminism originated in the West, so its concepts and philosophies are predominantly Western. But some of the ideas on which such philosophies are framed are also inherent in perceptions about women in the rest of the world. Western society has been continually patriarchal, that is to say, man is the whole and sole responsible for all the activities of the society as pointed out by Adrienne Rich, Frederick Engels, Simone de Beauvoir, Kate Millet, Betty Friedan and others. Bell Hooks (1984) claims that the ultimate objective of the overall activity of the feminist writers is the struggle against sexist oppression. Therefore, it is necessarily a struggle to eradicate the ideology of domination that permeates Western culture on various levels, as well as a commitment to reorganizing society so that the self-development of people can take precedence over imperialism, economic expansion and material desires (p. 23).

After the Second World War, a new generation of female writers emerged which did not accept the traditional status of women. Tuhina Mukherjee (2015a) states that “Feminist activists have joined hands to revolt social, religious, institutional, habitual practices that create second class citizen. The desire to achieve women's rights, like the right to live free of battery and abuse, the right to be free from sexual exploitation” (p. 229). Thus, they rebel against their social status, raising the agonized outcry of their own existence in order to overcome the patriarchal tradition of hegemony and silence. The second half of the twentieth century did not witness a shift only in feminism but almost in all walks of life including ancient heritage elements that were viewed as sacred and untouchable (Alwaqaa, 2024). Through their poetry, Elizabeth Bishop, Anne Sexton, and Adrienne Rich seek to reevaluate man-woman relationship and revise the gender postulates on which Western culture and civilization stand on.

Review of the Published Literature

The published collections of poetry by Bishop, Sexton, and Rich are considerably wide. However, the published work on their poetry is still scanty. Bishop's collection of poetry entitled *North & South* won her The Annual Poetry Prize in 1949. It is no surprise that she was the first twentieth-century woman poet

to be included in The Library of America. With the exception of Robert Lowell, it would be difficult to find a poet who, with her first book, secured a prominent place in the literary circle. The book received mixed responses. *A Cold Spring*, a new compilation of poetry, brought Bishop the Pulitzer Prize. The poems included in it were praised as more mature than the earlier ones. Bishop's last promising project was a volume of poetry titled *Geography III*, but she managed to complete only nine poems. Not until the publication of this warmest book, did Bishop begin to speak publicly of herself as a feminist and more candidly about the limiting factors that shaped her art: her era, sex, situation and education. With the publication of David Kalstone's *Becoming a Poet: Elizabeth Bishop with Marianne Moore, and Robert Lowell* in 1989, the appearance of just two years later of major studies by Lorrie Goldensohn and Bonnie Costello, and the promise of several revelatory biographies and critical studies, Bishop's scholarship is at last coming of age.

To Bedlam and Part Way Back (1960) was Sexton's first published book of poetry. It garnered good reviews. In 1961, *The Starry Night* was published, and in 1962, *All My Pretty Ones* came into existence and *Live or Die* was released in 1966. The last collection secured her Pulitzer Prize. *Love Poems* and her play *Mercy Street* were released in 1969 to be followed by *Transformation* in 1971. She published another compilation of poetry titled *The Book of Folly* in 1972. In the year of her death, 1974, Sexton was able to complete three further volumes of poetry: *The Death*

Notebooks, *The Awful Rowing toward God*, and *45 Mercy Street*. The last two volumes were published posthumously. The common major characteristic of Sexton's works is the confessional mode of her writing. She is seen as the modern model of the confessional feminist poet who transparently puts her heart naked on paper.

The same year of her graduation from college in 1951, Rich was selected by W. H. Auden for The Yale Series of Younger Poets Award for her first published volume of poems, *A Change of World*. *The Diamond Cutters*, her second compilation of poetry got published in 1955 with the birth of her first son. The duties of mothering combined with household chores occupied her time and not before the passage of eight years that Rich found time to write again. Rich's book of poetry, *Snapshots of a Daughter-in-Law* (1963), firmly established her reputation and rise to national fame. In this collection, as well as *Necessities of Life*, her third volume, published in 1966, Rich openly began to address political and gender issues. Her next two volumes, *Leaflets* (1969), and *The Will to Change* (1971) continued to treat women's themes.

Rich's political activism as she was increasingly involved in Vietnam antiwar movement along with her leading role in social movements including feminism informed her subsequent compilations of poetry. These collections are *Diving into the Wreck* (1973), *Twenty One Love Poems* (1976), *The Dream of a Common Language* (1978), *A Wild Patience Has Taken Me This Far* (1981), *The Fact of a Doorframe*

(1984) and prose works as *Of Woman Born: Motherhood as Experience and Institution* (1976) and *On Lies, Secrets, and Silence, Selected Prose* (1979). She published more works of poetry and prose; *Your Native Land, Your Life* (1986), *Blood, Bread and Poetry: Selected Prose, 1966–1978* (1986), and *Time's Power: Poems, 1985–1988* (1988). She was honored with the National Book Award in 1974 for her masterpiece volume, *Diving into the Wreck*. She shared this award with Alice Walker and Audre Lorde in the name of all silenced and oppressed women.

In 1997, she declined The National Medal of the Arts offered to her by President Clinton. She revealed the reason behind her rejection in one of her letters. She writes, "I could not accept such an award from President Clinton or this White House, because the very meaning of art as I understand it is incompatible with the cynical politics of this administration" (2006, p. 56). Rich's literary production continued in the last two decades of the twentieth and twenty first centuries publishing more books of poetry; *An Atlas of the Difficult World* (1991), *Dark Fields of the Republic* (1995), *Midnight Salvage* (1999), *The School among the Ruins* (2004), *Telephone Ringing in the Labyrinth* (2007), and *Tonight No Poetry Will Serve* (2010).

The published research on these poets' works is very scanty. In a dissertation entitled *The Feministic Aspects in the Poetry of Adrienne Rich, Anne Sexton and Elizabeth Bishop*, Mujahid Alwaqaa (2016) explores the feministic aspects in the poetry of these three poets in details. He tackles important themes such as the quest for a new female identity, the oppression exercised against women by patriarchy, and the sense of revolt in their poetry. Besides, there are other couple of reviews found here and there for the works of these three American woman poets, but I cannot find full-fledged research papers on the works of the American feminists. Thus, the current study may add some dimensions to the feminist perspectives of these poets.

Discussion and Analysis

Among American women writers who initiated the feminist activities in America and significantly contributed to the progressive march of feminist movement are Elizabeth Bishop, a poet interested in the close analysis of reality with poems that offer the reader multi-layered interpretations; Anne Sexton, a writer who explores the role of women in a society where she feels alienation from herself and from other human beings; and Adrienne Rich whose politics and language reflect the experience of women and more concretely her own.

Being aware of their roles as female artists, Bishop, Rich and Sexton raise their voices in order to stress their female existence and selfhood. They offer a new vision of sexuality and human relationships and a new conception of the world in which they live. They attempt to transmute their experience into poetry, exploring their own reality from different points of view so as to convey a new conception of

women. They explore the different roles women play all along their life, the alienation that they have suffered for many years, their vulnerability, their sexuality and their complexity as human beings. Thus, in their opinion, patriarchal customs and conventions bury a housewife in domestic drudge.

These women poets are conscious of the imbalance of power in social and love relationships as is evident in their writing. They refuse to reconcile with woman's position as an object; they want for themselves the status of an equal partner in the game. The menial domestic duties are nauseating and repulsive to them. They always describe domestic routine with a tinge of irony or in plain understatement.

Because of the feminist activism of these writers and others, a lot of changes occurred in America regarding women rights. A close reading of the poem, "Miami," reveals Bishop as approaching the subject of sexual relationships in a transitional society. In this poem she attacks the cheap exploitation of women's body by patriarchy which views women as an object for the males' sexual gratification. Bishop, this time, puts her argument in relation with Keats' poem, "Eve of St Agnes." "Miami" is an outstanding poem inspired by Keats' poem characterized by its powerful chivalry, steep gothicism, and mythological and religious symbolism. In this poem, a modern and secular affair occurs in a shabby and dirty hotel. Bishop's poetic style challenges the reader's imagination to unravel the complex and latent structures of meaning with which this poem is packed.

Bishop attempts to maintain an objective voice and stance towards the illicit affair taking place in a modern social setting. This accounts for her deliberate crossing out the word 'adulterous' in the second draft of the poem. Perhaps, she does so to point out that the taboos surrounding this word needs to be revised. In composing this poem, Bishop draws on romantic literature, especially the works of Keats and Coleridge. She looks to Coleridge for guidance in terms of technique so as to achieve naturalness and gracefulness, while she turns to Keats for pictorial and sensual inspiration.

The legend of the mesmerizing beauty of La Belle Dame Sans Merci together with St. Agnes' vitalizing story of chastity provides Bishop an appropriate context to compare and contrast the aspects of love in post-war America. Keats' poem attracts Bishop's attention to a famous fourth century female saint whose tale of piety and purity becomes constructive and regenerative. In the light of this legend, Bishop, in "Miami" exposes the gap between the old and modern times. Marriage, love and sexuality are no longer sacred in the modern, secularized world.

As the medieval legend reveals, the young Agnes chooses to remain chaste, so she spurns all the advances of her suitors. As a result, she is accused of being a devout Christian, then arrested and sentenced by a Roman court. She is punished by taking her to a house of prostitution; however, all men who dared take a lustful look at her are stricken with blindness. The Roman church stresses Agnes' steadfastness and strong faith extolling the excellent virtue of her sexual abstinence. The fathers of the church admire her

abnegation of the carnal pleasure and voyeurism: the forbidden gaze of mere mortals.

The martyrdom of Saint Agnes becomes a cult which underscores the female purity and the inviolable sanctity of marriage. Over centuries, Saint Agnes' story takes on a mythical significance to the extent that young girls who perform particular rituals and rites on the eve of her feast day may meet their prospective husbands in dreams.

In "Miami" the lovers are transported to a twentieth century setting, in a cheap hotel in Florida. The speaker describes the hotel room as well as the scene outside.

across the bay the tattered screens of lines of scorched
Australian pines
The smell of fried potatoes from below
The hot air pulses
the long-bladed fan, black and quarter-fed
and at your head
a ten-cent store reading lamp
[and] two soiled telephone books
filled with their thousands of names
and none of them are ours thank God
in the dark drawer undoubtedly a Gideon Bible.
Endless crowds in cottons, toilet waters,
[buy] shoes at Burdines, place their bets,
drink coconut milk (p. 78).

The speaker is strikingly photographing the scene outside from the window of the hotel room. A multitude of holiday-makers can be seen milling about in the streets. The whole scene seems to be thriving with vitality and exuberance as the speaker refers to the aspects of the contemporary living and well-known commercial names such as the Gillette blade and Burdines department store. However, the hotel room appears to be meager and shabby in which a modern-day love affair is carried out in a stark defiance to the values of the traditional society and the message conveyed by Keats' poem. These lovers constitute a substantial part of a tainted and taboo-breaking reality where even the glimmer of the bay is 'sleazy'. Their names are not found in the telephone book because they belong to another city.

The speaker wonders whether their love affair is adulterous, unusual and ridiculous. She thinks that modern love is primarily born out of physical desire, where woman is seen as a sex commodity serving the selfish desires of patriarchy. In the following lines, the tone suddenly shifts, and the setting moves from the stifling heat of Miami beach to a cooler and more tranquil place. Readers recognize a dream

world.

As if by the freshest brooks, in shades
Where shepherds sing, they (went to sleep) fell
asleep
(by) five o'clock from love that was
absurd, (adulterous), and deep (p. 79).

The definition of love, in this case, as deep and ridiculous stands in contrast with the Keatsian notion of love rituals surrounding the legend of Saint Agnes. The absurdity and illicitness of love is described with abstract nouns which perhaps add to the judgmental note of the poem. This, however, stands at odds with Bishop's usually restrained and descriptive language. The crossing out of the word 'adulterous' can be taken as either the poet's approval of the affair or her refusal to pass judgment on its moral basis. Two contrastive worlds are presented in the poem. The old one with its spirituality where love is ideally true, sacred and meaningful and the modern, secular one in which love is seen as corrupt, cheap and silly. The lovers have no pangs to conform to or escape from social conventions. Generally speaking, this poem proves that Bishop willingly explores relationships conducted privately with their rebellious connotations.

Like Bishop's rebellious verse, Sexton's poem (1999) entitled "Consorting with Angels" is an outcry of a woman who has been stuck in the household chores. The cumulative burden of routine domesticity is poignantly expressed in this poem. Monotony and the boring daily tasks deprive married women of any self-worth or a horizon of creative change. Being robbed of any chance of asserting her dignity and individuality, the woman speaker considers herself a slave destined to utter obedience and social conformity. Sexton reveals her determination to dispel the magic line of the patriarchal sugar-coated ideology of power and dominance. She struggles hard to create a fulfilling and autonomous existence for herself and women in general. The will to do so is courageously stated in this poem and other poems which are an amalgam of a defiant rejection of patriarchal taboos and values. However, the speaker's irresolvable hesitation and ambivalence in taking the ultimate decision to break the social taboos renders her as both a rebellious and submissive character.

Sexton figures out that the male-dominated society does not garner any consideration or weight for either the spiritual aspirations or the intellectual ambitions of women. Her household objects often act as symbols of a life in prison. These objects drive her heroines to violence, revolt and even frustration and madness. "Consorting with Angels" begins with the explicit expression of fatigue and boredom at the sight of such domestic articles; "I was tired of being a woman, / tired of the spoons and the pots."

The poet's special consideration of her worth as a woman with poetic gifts makes her feminist

concerns, pivotal in all her poems, loom more than some contemporary poets. The poem under discussion has references to Joan of Arc who revolted against oppression and injustices, and who was mercilessly tortured to death. In fact, she was held at the stake and fire was set on her to be burned alive in man's clothes following a long period of cruel imprisonment and persecution. Sexton conveys the message that the unjust and inhumane punishment of Joan of Arc is the dilemma of every contemporary housewife when she thinks to play new roles outside the ones prescribed by patriarchy. The speaker of the poem is an exhausted woman who becomes tired of her womanhood and bored of the gender of things. Gender has become a curse to her life and turns out to be at the center of woman's predicament. She takes an imaginary journey through the world of dreams where people, regardless of their gender, become sexless angels; "each one like a poem obeying itself / performing God's functions." She; however, is conscious of the fact that the genderless world is only a wish-fulfillment and that there is no way escaping gender barriers. It seems that the speaker's disgust and indignation primarily originate in man's reluctance to recognize her as a rational partner; a companion who has the capacity to make his life perfect and more ordered.

As the dreamy domestic mask tears off, Sexton sees the reality of her situation horribly naked. She feels a gloomy sense of dissatisfaction and incompleteness about her life. She takes poetry as a therapy tool at the counsel of her psychiatrist, Martin Orne, and this in effect prolongs her life and changes her preconceptions. In an interview with Patricia Marx, she reasserts her inclination towards poetry saying: "I think probably I'm an artist at heart, and I've found my own form, which I think is poetry" (1985, p. 30). Poetry liberates her from the snares of the feminine mystique and the false American dream and places her on the pedestal of freedom and individuality. Yet, domestic frustration and discordant relationships lead her to suffering, revolt, then to ultimate insanity.

"Housewife" is another poem in which Sexton reprimands the housewife who is totally preoccupied with homemaking and domestic activities that may ultimately debilitate her mind, drain her potentials, and divert her away from pursuing a more meaningful life. She writes, "some women marry houses / It's another kind of skin; it has a heart, / a mouth, a liver, and bowel movements" (1999, p. 77). The poet says ironically that some women identify themselves with houses which they passionately love. Ben Howard (1988) suggests that the image of the housewife evokes the horror of the suppressed violence and irrational fear a woman enmeshed in domestic routine. Mrs. Sexton's personal tragedy seems to have been bound up in domestic objects, both as literal impediments and as symbols of her role; and through those objects she seems to have been developing, at the end of her life, a vision of her predicament (p. 182).

The speaker seems to ridicule the housewife who is ready to exchange her real life with an inanimate object called house. The poet blames her as she chooses to lead a narrow and death-like life. She, further,

raises an accusing finger at patriarchy-bound mothers who viciously try to shape their daughters in accordance with the male-centralized culture which considers housekeeping the ultimate end for women; “Men enter by force, draw back like Jonah / Into their fleshy mothers. / A woman is her mother. / That's the main thing (1999, p. 77).

The poem is grounded on two parallel equivalences: woman equals her mother and woman equals her house. Woman's identification with the house appears to be absolute and irreversible; however, this type of identification obscures women and endangers their self-existence. The poem, thus, embodies the idea of the compulsory confinement and resignation of women. Once the woman is married, she feels isolated and alienated from the rest of the world. The idea of the wife being protected by the husband from the outside is ironically highlighted.

Many women, joined to a man through the bonds of marriage, are obliged to break with their past and to face up to a new life devoted to their family, their husbands and children. In this sense, women lose their previous autonomy so as to enter a world which is different, in many cases, from that which they wish for. Although there are many women who accept the role of the wife with all its consequences, there are some women who fight against the confinement and surrender that marriage imposes on them. Thus, they try to change those traditional roles and values imposed on them through marriage. Therefore, a new vision of the marital state in which the woman, like the man, keeps her own individuality and identity is necessitated in Sexton's opinion. Thus, the image of marriage as a close room, as a cage in which the woman is secluded, gives way to a vision of human relationships where the individual has freedom to think and act.

The frustration and discontent of a housewife in a traditional family is, likewise, depicted in Rich's poem “Aunt Jennifer's Tigers.” This poetic masterpiece can be applied to all housewives undergoing the same domestic drudgeries. In fact, this poem is a talking picture of the husband's hegemony, the wife's hard reality of oppression and her trial to come out of it. The protesting speaker enumerates the hardships of a married woman, and the restrictions marriage has incurred on her life. Rich finds this abominable and unbearable. She attempts to describe the futility of lust, the dullness of domesticity, and the artificial marital comforts that guarantee man's domination on woman.

The speaker identifies herself with the female addressee in the poem which underscores the unpleasant aspects of the wife-husband relationship. She denounces the aberrations and ritual taboos of married life as well as the casual manifestation of a male egocentrism and self-importance with all its horrid display. Man's indifference and selfishness reduce women to sub-human dwarfs and the family to a little four-walled room. Male's ego transforms the woman into a grotesque creature with a diminished personality.

The husband wants to tame the woman by any means; however, the woman in the poem resists this domestication through her work of art. Unfortunately, in the long process of domestication, she is gradually deprived of her urge to fly.

Aunt Jennifer's fingers fluttering through the wool
Find even the ivory needle hard to pull.
The massive weight of Uncle's wedding band
Sits heavily upon Aunt Jennifer's hand (1959, p. 4).

Rich's observation on social oppression and the necessity to rise in revolt against the hegemony of man is expressed in her poems where the oppression of women and their desire for freedom are depicted in the domestic suffocation of the housewives and in the sharp inner conflict of a married woman who craves to be an artist. In "Aunt Jennifer's Tigers," the sentiments of oppression and revolt are manifest as the reader perceives a housewife who silently endures domestic burdens. She, at the same time, immerses herself in artwork as a protest against the patriarchal assignments for women to play the role of a submissive wife and an obedient housewife.

The contrast between a docile housewife and a revolutionary artist is sharp. The poet vividly delineates the tragic situation and the severe predicament of a conventionally married woman living under the power of a rigidly patriarchal system. The tigers painted and embroidered by the woman artist in the tapestry serve as a projection of women's sense of dissatisfaction and indignation at the conventions of society. This piece of artistry, also, reveals her longing for freedom.

Aunt Jennifer's tigers prance across a screen,
Bright topaz denizens of a world of green.
They do not fear the men beneath the trees;
They pace in sleek chivalric certainty (1959, p. 4).

Stanza three accentuates the point that the patriarchal domination over woman is a life-long process and the marital cuffs bind her forever. In Rich's view, the plight of women being tormented by patriarchy will carry on up to the moment of death unless they revolt against the conventional and traditional institutions and taboos that stand as obstacles to their liberation.

When Aunt is dead, her terrified hand will lie
Still ringed with ordeals she was mastered by.
The tigers in the panel that she made
Will go on prancing, proud and unafraid (1959, p. 4).

So, in this poem, the dilemma of a female artist is revealed in the contrast between art world represented by tapestry and the real daily domestic activities of her life. Claire Keyes states that "The complex interaction

between the womanly role and the role of woman as artist, considered by society aberrant, forms a thematic nucleus in Rich's early poetry" (1986, p. 21). Therefore, the tigers portrayed in Aunt Jennifer's artistic piece of work suggest the creative and constructive power of art and the artist's strong desire to undermine the foolish restrictions and taboos of patriarchy.

The wide gap between Aunt Jennifer's real situation and her imaginary work not only denotes the aspiration of married women for freedom, but it also depicts the crisis and frustration of a woman artist working within a male-dominated literary ideology. The female artist is torn apart between her outside subservience and inside insurgency. Rich is conscious of the complex situation of a creatively inclined woman who strives to change the current social order by means of tools of literature. Oftentimes, the search for this change may end up in frustration.

Rich, thus, registers her protest against patriarchal imperatives imposed on intelligent and sensitive women whose existence seems to be fake and peripheral in such a vapid male culture. She demonstrates that man's tyranny turns out to be the outcome resulting from his incapacity to love, respect and accept woman as his equal partner. This poem unequivocally underscores the callousness and cruelty of the male-centered world. It is, also, a powerful expression of uncurbed indignation and wrath at the inhumane treatment and cruelties unleashed on the oppressed and repressed females.

The initial attraction or American dream, as Sexton calls it, of having a house and children of one's own turns into a shadow and a horrible nightmare. In Bishop's juvenilia poem "Once on a hill I met a man," the female character is attracted to a small home by an enticing man who apparently seems to be both loving and appealing. As soon as she gets into the tiny house, she is completely locked away by him and is accompanied by people from the shadow world and fairy tales; "knights and princesses ... / And people from the fabled moon." Motifs from fairy tales are used by the poet to comment on the marital house as being a prison into which women are enticed by handsome but deceptive men who weave words into magic so as to woo them into their destruction. To establish a house is a powerful symbol of marriage, unity, safety, and comfort; however, the house turns out as a real jail, an idea which contradicts the romantic relationship between the speaker-poet and the space he occupies or captures (Alwaqaa, Though the speaker says that she knows every witch-word used by these opportunists, she cannot escape, and eventually refuses to leave her prison for fear of the man's retribution and severe revenge. Therefore, the house for a wife becomes her prison and the marriage document turns out to be her imprisonment sentence. A jail where the jail-keeper exercises all different kinds of physical and psychological tortures and oppression on his helpless creature is depicted in this poem.

Just like Bishop's poems, Rich's "Snapshots of a Daughter-in-Law," included in her 1963 collection of poetry carrying the same title, is considered the first overtly feminist poem. Mukherjee (2015b) comments

on the significance of this volume by stating that this “volume shows a kind of movement from mild objections against patriarchal norms to harsh allegations against destructive masculinity crushing life out of women. Rich has realized that sufferings of women are universal. Marriage and motherhood have been made tools for oppression. Home is not the only source of happiness, rather satisfaction comes only when one is able to experience the full flowering of one's personality” (p. 211).

Rich's poem directly expresses her need and interest in resisting and rebelling both as a woman and as a poet against the age-long values of patriarchy. She writes about the community of women whose capabilities and gifts have been muffled, buried and aborted and whose very beings have been thwarted and silenced. In one snapshot of the poem, the belle of Shreveport has been denied her own potentials and talents by rigorously conforming to romantic feminine ideals and she is now moldering away like the remnants of her wedding cake. This horrible image of decay and degeneration reflects the tragedy of women within the traditional confines of marriage. The daughter of the belle of Shreveport nervously “wipes the teaspoons” Tense and agitated by what could be her destiny, she decides to break away from the current patriarchal laws and rules and “grow[s] another way.”

In another scenic snapshot, Corinna deceptively denies her own talents to sing the words and music of women. Rich expresses her regret and indignation that Corinna is seduced by images of beauty and the concept of romantic love perpetuated by the patriarchal philosophy. Yet, Rich acknowledges and values women who refuse to conform to patriarchal conventions. She asserts that women should not settle for mediocrity and a world where “time is male.” In her opinion, the current situation of women is a big tragedy, articulating in the final snapshot of the poem a vision of a thinking and powerful woman who no longer heeds patriarchal seductions.

The second section of the poem concerns a woman who thinks that she is going crazy because of her ignoble situation and constant domestic drudgery. However, she is haunted by voices telling her to resist and rebel. Voices which she can hear but not obey.

Banging the coffee-pot into the sink
she hears the angels chiding, and looks out
past the raked gardens to the sloppy sky.
Only a week since They said: *Have no patience*

The next time it was: *Be insatiable.*

Then: *Save yourself; others you cannot save*

Sometimes she's left the tapstream scald her arm,

a match burn to her thumbnail,
or held her hand above the kettle's snout
right in the wooly stream.

They are probably angels (1994, p. 23).

The speaker's breakdown is caused by the passionate need to rebel and her powerlessness to do so. Yet, she tries to transform her tragic reality by the "Necessary Angel of imagination." Rich makes a distinction between the passive day-dreaming and the active, subversive processes of imagination.

This highly autobiographical poem exemplifies the speaker's conflict between sitting in passivity or rising in revolt. Rich explores the risks and challenges encountered by the woman protagonist by placing her amid representations of femininity drawn from the classical texts that produce a "girlhood frozen into forms." One of the messages the poet offers is the clear rejection of the woman-degrading statements such as Diderot's "You all die at fifteen," and creates a "Nervy, glowering" daughter who "grows another way." As the poem proceeds and the woman of each snapshot becomes more conscious of her oppression, exploitation and potential, the poet presents her arguments with growing confidence, hopeful of change.

In the final stanza the poet optimistically predicts a future "delivered, palpable, ours," leaving readers with a clear understanding of her anticipation of a society that does not oppress women and treat them on an equal basis. As the poem suggests, the primary way to break the magic spell of femininity in the way to women's liberation from the shackles of patriarchy is to engage in a "radical critique of culture and literature" (Rich, *On Lies, Secrets, and Silence*, p. 35).

Thus, to construct the female story and the feminist history, women writers should transform the old conventions and forms into more useful and inclusive materials through a process of rereading, rewriting and reconceptualizing; a process which primarily depends on the personal perspectives. As a result, Rich's creative and critical work based on tales which tune in with the difficulties the woman who tries to write encounters as she is confronted with visions of femininity propagated for in male-authored texts where she has immersed herself during her formative years. This poem is, thus, considered one of the few early poems found in Rich's poetic oeuvre composed solely from a female standpoint in which she explicitly and directly attacks the male-dominated institutions of marriage, male literary canon and women's miserable situation.

According to Rich, encumbered by love, many women, in one way or another, may confine themselves in the wedlock jail just like a bird that has been trapped into a cage. Kate Millet (1990) observes that marriage and romantic love obscure the realities of female life in a patriarchy. She considers romantic

love “a means of emotional manipulation of the female by the male” (pp. 61-67). As soon as they realize that they have been manipulated and deceived by enchanting words of love, some women resort to the work of art which provides them with ways to silently express their protest and discontent as it is the case with Aunt Jennifer. Readers can see Aunt Jennifer's decorated work of art as a means of expressing her dissatisfaction and dissonance with her current marital conditions. Some other women, projected in Rich's poems, voice their anger and demonstrate their rebellion against oppression and lack of will in more aggressive and bolder ways. This anger is manifested as an outrageous monster inside women's minds or materialized in their eccentric acts. Through simple objects and domestic life routines, these poets thread out crucial gender themes as they delve deeper into the consciousness of the readers and upset their thinking and perception. This poetic technique is significant in creating dialogues through which perceptions are changed and understanding is obtained (Alwaqaa, 2024).

Conclusion

It can be said that Bishop forms a new poetic expression: being a woman and a writer demands a new perception of life and the male culture that exploits women and the vulnerable. Through her poetry, she attempts to expose the stupid laws and absurdities of a patriarchally-dominated society, though covertly, and to express the need to change this male-oriented culture. However, she laments the loss of the innocent and spiritual love in the ancient world in comparison with the dirty physical love of modern life which is based on utter lust. Bishop; however, remains a puzzling and mysterious figure that needs to be decoded by critics and readers. She, of course, belongs to the school of reticence but it is a well-known fact that she has a sexual orientation and a clear vision of the desired society that should exist for the sake of salvaging women and other oppressed groups.

Rich and Sexton, on the other hand, pour their lives into their poems, speaking of the unspeakable, and shunning the rest of the tight-knit literary and social world. With this step forward, they are alone in their verse. They vehemently scorn the foolish institutions of patriarchy and aggressively attack them; their philosophy is clear to all. Through difficult life and bitter experiences, Sexton provides women new insights into themselves and the patriarchal machine that strives to keep them jailed forever while Rich transgresses all the patriarchal boundaries as she insistently calls for a rebellion against all the existing values which she thinks that they are male-constructed ones.

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